

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinteractions/usnm
hash://md5/c82bd55cd7ad5a0fb4ae89c3c7eb97a2

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named globalbioticinteractions/usnm, has fingerprint hash://md5/c82bd55cd7ad5a0fb4ae89c3c7eb97a2, is 4.80GiB in size and contains 281,641 interactions with 7 unique types of associations (e.g., hasHost) between 33,245 primary taxa (e.g., Nematoda) and 29,708 associated taxa (e.g., Ovis aries). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

NMNH_Botany (US) - Version 1.4 https://collections.nmnh.si.edu/ipt/archive.do?r=nmnh_botany_2026-06-02T20:21:27.157Z NMNH Extant Specimen Records (USNM, US) - Version 1.109 https://collections.nmnh.si.edu/ipt/archive.do?r=nmnh_extant_dwca_2026-06-02T20:21:27.157Z NMNH Material Samples (USNM) - Version 1.90 https://collections.nmnh.si.edu/ipt/archive.do?r=nmnh_material_sample_2026-06-02T20:21:27.157Z nmnh_materialsample_test - Version 1.49 https://collections.nmnh.si.edu/ipt/archive.do?r=nmnh_materialsample_test_2026-06-02T20:21:27.157Z nmnh_occurrence_archive - Version 1.18 https://collections.nmnh.si.edu/ipt/archive.do?r=nmnh_occurrence_archive_2026-06-02T20:21:27.157Z Occurrence data of Acronyches (Diptera: Asilidae: Leptogastrinae) - Version 1.1 https://collections.nmnh.si.edu/ipt/archive.do?r=acronyches_2026-06-02T20:21:27.157Z Occurrence data of Afrotropical Mydidae (Insecta: Diptera: Asiloidea) - Version 1.5 https://collections.nmnh.si.edu/ipt/archive.do?r=afrotropical_2026-06-02T20:21:27.157Z Occurrence data of Anasillomos (Diptera: Asiloidea: Asilidae) - Version 5.23 https://collections.nmnh.si.edu/ipt/archive.do?r=anasillomos_2026-06-02T20:21:27.157Z Occurrence data of Asilidae at Gobabeb, Namib Desert, Namibia (10 km radius) - Version 1.3 <https://collections.nmnh.si.edu/ipt/archive.do?r=gobabebasilidae>

2026-06-02T20:21:27.157Z Occurrence data of Mydidae at Gobabeb, Namib Desert, Namibia (10 km radius) - Version 1.2 <https://collections.nmnh.si.edu/ipt/archive.do?r=gobabebmydidae>
2026-06-02T20:21:27.157Z Occurrence data of Prytanomyia (Diptera: Asiloidea: Asilidae) - Version 1.22 <https://collections.nmnh.si.edu/ipt/archive.do?r=prytanomyia>
2026-06-02T20:21:27.157Z hash://md5/c82bd55cd7ad5a0fb4ae89c3c7eb97a2

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.11
nomer	0.6.5
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 4.80GiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/usnm

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/usnm \
> review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/usnm \
> interactions.tsv
```

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/usnm`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/usnm`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/usnm`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/usnm`)

```
# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/usnm \
| nomer append col \
> name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

You can find a copy of the full review script at [check-data.sh](#). See also [GitHub](#) and [Codeberg](#).

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

An extensive list of files produced as part of the review process can be found in [Appendix A. Review Files](#).

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/usnm`, has fingerprint hash: `//md5/c82bd55cd7ad5a0fb4ae89c3c7eb97a2`, is 4.80GiB in size and contains 281,641 interactions with 7 unique types of associations (e.g., `hasHost`)

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

between 33,245 primary taxa (e.g., Nematoda) and 29,708 associated taxa (e.g., *Ovis aries*).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped csv, tsv, geopackage and parquet archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped html page at indexed-interactions.html.gz are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 2: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Morishitium urocissae	hasHost	Urocissa erythrorhynga	http://n2t.net/ark:/65665/300001402-3207-4d7a-9943-0c4668f6ea02
Columnnea dissimilis	adjacentTo	tree at forest edge	http://n2t.net/ark:/65665/3000115b0-526d-4efd-a507-8084242653d5
Parmotrema subochraceum	adjacentTo	tree.	http://n2t.net/ark:/65665/3000137ab-cdcf-4f90-a6aa-86942fb1dd1f
Aploparaksis daviesi	hasHost	Arenaria interpres	http://n2t.net/ark:/65665/300015b13-009e-4fb5-a316-ec7b6bdce720

Table 3: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
hasHost	163243
adjacentTo	109125
interactsWith	8973

interactionTypeName	count
killedBy	213
eats	67
visits	19
visitsFlowersOf	1

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Nematoda	3985
Cestoda	3058
Trematoda	1757
Sphaerodactylus macrolepis	1237
Myelochroa aurulenta	1230
Haemonchus contortus	1176
Physaloptera sp.	1008
Cladonia furcata	918
Lobaria pulmonaria	839
Cladonia squamosa	777
Cladonia cristatella	777
Acanthocephala	708
Heterodermia obscurata	699
Indet. sp.	686
Cladonia grayi	664
Graphis scripta	630
Lobaria quercizans	630
Leptogium cyanescens	606
Cladonia verticillata	606

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
Ovis aries	6041
Bos taurus	4962
Equus caballus	4278
Canis familiaris	3548
rocks	3334
Odocoileus virginianus	2399
Felis domestica	1696

targetTaxonName	count
Homo sapiens	1669
tree	1566
Sus scrofa domestica	1484
Ochotona princeps	1422
trees	1212
soil	1130
Gallus gallus	1108
Ovibos moschatus	1100
Cervus elaphus	882
Procyon lotor	880
sandstone	871
Branta canadensis	866

Table 6: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
Haemonchus contortus	hasHost	Ovis aries	618
Sphaerodactylus macrolepis	interactsWith	vegetation removal plot (Cocolob 1) in Cocolobo uvifera forest at E end of grassy (mown) area.	593
Moniezia expansa	hasHost	Ovis aries	551
Trematoda	hasHost	Branta canadensis	415
Moniezia trigonophora	hasHost	Ovis aries	410
Cephaluris sp.	hasHost	Ochotona princeps	388
Sphaerodactylus macrolepis	interactsWith	vegetation removal plot (Cocolob 2) in coastal strand Cocolobo uvifera forest, ca. 10 m inland from beach.	375

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
Ostertagia ostertagi	hasHost	Bos taurus	359
Nematoda	hasHost	Ovibos moschatus	350
Eugenuris talkeetnaeuris	hasHost	Ochotona princeps	314
Mazamastrongylus odocoilei	hasHost	Odocoileus virginianus	304
Taenia pisiformis	hasHost	Canis familiaris	290
Ancylostoma caninum	hasHost	Canis familiaris	290
Oesophagostomum columbianum	hasHost	Ovis aries	276
Sphaerodactylus macrolepis	interactsWith	vegetation removal plot (Acacia 2) in Leucaena leu- cophala/Acacia macrocantha forest (16-18 years old) at E end of grassy (mown) area, just NW of garden area.	261
Cooperia punctata	hasHost	Bos taurus	260
Moniezia planissima	hasHost	Bos taurus	258
Spiculopteragia asymmetrica	hasHost	Cervus elaphus	252
Taenia saginata	hasHost	Homo sapiens	252

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

You can download the indexed dataset under review at indexed-interactions.csv.gz. A tab-separated file can be found at indexed-interactions.tsv.gz

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download svg

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution. These maps were generated using MapServer (McKenna et al. 2025) tools configured via map configuration indexed-interactions.map :

```
MAP
  SIZE 1600 800
  EXTENT -180 -90 180 90
  PROJECTION
    "init=epsg:4326"
  END
  LAYER # MODIS WMS map from NASA
    NAME      "modis_nasa"
    TYPE      RASTER
    OFFSITE   0 0 0
    STATUS    ON
    CONNECTIONTYPE WMS
    CONNECTION "https://gibs.earthdata.nasa.gov/wms/epsg4326/best/wms.cgi?"

  METADATA
    "wms_srs" "EPSG:4326"
```

```

        "wms_name" "OSM_Land_Water_Map"
        "wms_server_version" "1.1.1"
        "wms_format" "image/jpeg"
    END
    CLASS
        STYLE
            COLOR          232 232 232
            OUTLINECOLOR  32 32 32
        END
    END
END
LAYER
    NAME "indexed-interactions"
    TYPE POLYGON
    STATUS ON
    CONNECTIONTYPE OGR
    CONNECTION "indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg"
    DATA "indexed-interactions-h3"
    CLASS
        STYLE
            COLORRANGE 253.0 231.0 37.0 32.0 164.0 134.0
            DATARANGE 0.3010299956639812 3.9925093350677754
            RANGEITEM "log_number_of_records"
            OUTLINECOLOR 0 0 0
        END
    END
END
END

```

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at indexed-interactions.gpkg for point data and indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Table 7: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Ton block coral algal rock	NONE	col	Ton block coral algal rock
Diameter log	NONE	col	Diameter log
Ft diam log	NONE	col	Ft diam log
Ton block coral algal rock taken anchor	NONE	col	Ton block coral algal rock taken anchor

Table 8: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	23766
col	class	19
col	family	192
col	form	8
col	genus	2942
col	gigaclass	1

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	infraorder	3
col	kingdom	3
col	order	32
col	parvphylum	1
col	phylum	16
col	species	29799
col	subclass	4
col	subfamily	2
col	subgenus	45
col	subphylum	2
col	subspecies	1071
col	superfamily	1
col	superorder	1
col	variety	87
discoverlife	NA	57737
discoverlife	species	3
gbif	NA	24325
gbif	class	19
gbif	family	193
gbif	form	29
gbif	genus	2942
gbif	kingdom	3
gbif	order	28
gbif	phylum	15
gbif	species	28871
gbif	subspecies	1163
gbif	variety	452
itis	NA	39834
itis	class	20
itis	division	1
itis	family	169
itis	genus	2136
itis	infraorder	1
itis	infraphylum	1
itis	kingdom	3
itis	order	34
itis	phylum	16
itis	section	1
itis	species	14511
itis	subclass	5
itis	subgenus	5
itis	subphylum	1
itis	subspecies	957
itis	superclass	1

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
itis	superfamily	1
itis	variety	58
mdd	NA	57739
ncbi	NA	37355
ncbi	clade	1
ncbi	class	18
ncbi	family	184
ncbi	genus	2457
ncbi	infraorder	2
ncbi	kingdom	1
ncbi	order	36
ncbi	phylum	17
ncbi	species	17190
ncbi	subclass	7
ncbi	subgenus	22
ncbi	suborder	1
ncbi	subphylum	1
ncbi	subspecies	453
ncbi	superclass	1
ncbi	varietas	14
pbdb	NA	53795
pbdb	class	18
pbdb	family	87
pbdb	genus	1070
pbdb	informal	1
pbdb	infraorder	1
pbdb	kingdom	3
pbdb	order	25
pbdb	phylum	16
pbdb	species	2665
pbdb	subclass	3
pbdb	subfamily	1
pbdb	subgenus	1
pbdb	subkingdom	1
pbdb	suborder	2
pbdb	subspecies	47
pbdb	superclass	1
pbdb	superorder	1
pbdb	tribe	1
pbdb	unranked clade	10
tpt	NA	56016
tpt	genus	241
tpt	species	1482
wfo	NA	48396

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
wfo	family	4
wfo	form	3
wfo	genus	607
wfo	phylum	1
wfo	section	1
wfo	species	8638
wfo	subspecies	83
wfo	variety	66
worms	NA	38980
worms	class	22
worms	family	185
worms	forma	1
worms	genus	2241
worms	gigaclass	1
worms	infraorder	2
worms	kingdom	3
worms	order	34
worms	parvphylum	1
worms	phylum	14
worms	phylum (division)	2
worms	species	16120
worms	subclass	6
worms	subfamily	2
worms	subgenus	7
worms	suborder	1
worms	subphylum	2
worms	subspecies	130
worms	superfamily	1
worms	tribe	1
worms	variety	9

Table 9: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	NONE	66350
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	63185

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	SYNONYM_OF	29676
discoverlife	NONE	146656
discoverlife	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	4
discoverlife	SYNONYM_OF	3
gbif	NONE	67165
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	68175
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	30457
itis	NONE	102466
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	38337
itis	SYNONYM_OF	6883
mdd	NONE	144082
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2383
mdd	SYNONYM_OF	60
ncbi	NONE	95989
ncbi	SAME_AS	45144
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	5935
ncbi	COMMON_NAME_OF	13
pbdb	NONE	136568
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	9099
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	1137
tpt	NONE	142611
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	3830
tpt	SYNONYM_OF	88
wfo	NONE	119992
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	22589
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	5809
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	1246
worms	NONE	104872
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	32324
worms	SYNONYM_OF	11035

Table 10: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in zipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in zipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in zipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in zipped html, csv, and tsv)

catalog name	alignment results
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 11: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-06-03T22:01:01Z	summary	https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/usnm/arch
2026-06-03T22:01:01Z	summary	281641 interaction(s)
2026-06-03T22:01:01Z	summary	0 note(s)
2026-06-03T22:01:01Z	summary	40 info(s)

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-06-04) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: "Open data is data that can be freely used, re-used and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike."

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

Acknowledgements

We thank the many humans that created us and those who created and maintained the data, software and other intellectual resources that were used for producing this review. In addition, we are grateful for the natural resources providing the basis for these human and bot activities. Also, thanks to <https://github.com/zygoballus> for helping improve the layout of the review tables.

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

Appendix A. Review Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format

filename	description
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map
indexed-interactions.map	mapserver configuration to plot species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review on a map

filename	description
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads

filename	description
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

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